

**SOME PERFORMANCE INVESTIGATIONS ON FADING
CHANNELS IN MOBILE AD HOC NETWORKS**

A SYNOPSIS

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) are considered by many researchers, since they show wider applications in many areas like Passenger safety, infotainment and emergency scenarios. Mobile ad hoc networks possess a flat network infrastructure. It has a shared medium, which is highly demandable for radio communication. In MANET architecture, every node is a router as well as end host. The nodes or devices in the MANET architecture are generally autonomous. MANET has a dynamic topological architecture, which highly promotes mobility. In the MANET architecture, every node also works as a router, since they route packets for other nodes. MANETs are a kind of Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs), but the difference is that the nodes move over the limited places. Wireless mobile network and usage of mobile devices are becoming increasingly popular, as they provide users access to information anytime anywhere. Mobile Ad hoc Networks (MANETs) are emerging as promising communication technology in situations such as emergency applications, military applications, and civilian applications, collaborative computing and communication in smaller areas. MANET topology changes often due to node/link failures, node joining/leaving and mobility of nodes. Thus, there are several issues in MANETs like routing, resource allocation, security, adaptability with heterogeneous platforms and devices, Quality of Service (QoS) management, power management, media access, channel management, addressing, mobility management, performance modeling, etc. Routing is one of the prominent issue in MANETs, that involves the route discovery and route maintenance among source and destination node pairs. The routing techniques in MANETs are unicast (one-to-one), multicast (one-to-many), any cast (one-to-one of many) and broadcast (one-to-all). To support real-time multimedia applications in unicast, multicast and any cast in MANETs, QoS must be guaranteed according to the user requirement. MANET nodes are connected by wireless links. Each node operates as an end system and a router for all other nodes in the network. Nodes are free to move and organize themselves in an arbitrary fashion. Ad hoc nodes communicate to their neighbours through wireless links within an area of influence. These networks have the nodes with high mobility and the nodes of network move in

the same or opposite directions. Because of the high mobility of the nodes, the network topology becomes dynamic. The nodes moving on different roads cannot establish communication among them, if there are blockades. Many MANETs employ broadcast communication scheme to transmit the information to all nodes come within the communication. This is known as data dissemination process. In this scheme, the data are not preserved; Data collision also occurs, when many vehicles retransmit the same data. Moreover the generated data must reach the all destination nodes within the specific time without any delay. Since the MANETs are dynamic network and the patterns change frequently, the information also may vary. These reasons make the broadcast in MANETs as a great concern. Since the density of nodes (Mobiles) varies for different times and on different roads, the broadcast scheme should function well in different scenarios. In a dense network, packet collisions and low packet delivery ratio problems occur. Many protocols are invented to reduce the broadcast storm concern in the traditional MANETs. However there are only few for MANET and they are not much reliable and efficient.

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this research work is to provide a Novel hybrid technique for reducing the fading problems in the MANET. For obtaining the main purpose of this research, the following objectives are to be fulfilled.

- Generate the Hybrid N.W gamma scheme
- Need to reduce the fading problems in MANET
- Implement a new algorithm for improving the performance of the fading channels
- Improving and upgrading the performance of the fading channel

3. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Fading can cause poor performance in a communication system, because it can result in a loss of signal power without reducing the power of the noise. This signal loss can be

over some or all of the signal bandwidth. Fading can also be a problem, as it changes over time. Communication systems are often designed to adapt to such impairments, but the fading can change faster than the adaptations can be made. Fading in MANET can cause networking transmission problems. Some of the parameters like average delay, throughput, jitter, and PDR play very important role in the performance of analysis and design of the mobile Ad-hoc network. Moreover, establishing paths with the highest performance is a challenging issue for reducing Path loss, Total Energy consumption, Average Bit error Rate, and improve Packet Delivery Ratio, Probability Density Function, and Data Transmission Rate.

4. THESIS ORGANIZATION

The entire research work is presented in the form of thesis and it has been organized as follows.

Chapter 1: This chapter discusses the introduction about Mobile ad hoc network, necessity of MANET, applications under MANET, advantages and disadvantages for QoS parameter in MANET environment.

Chapter 2: This chapter discusses about the various research methodologies proposed for in the earlier studies in order to determine the problem statement.

Chapter 3: This chapter discusses about the first stage of research to implement the hybrid N.W gamma scheme to improve the speed performance of MANET.

Chapter 4: This chapter discusses about the second stage of research work to implement QPSK based Grover searching algorithm for upgrading the performance of MANET.

Chapter 5: This chapter discusses about the research results and performance analysis with the other approaches.

Chapter 6: Findings and Suggestions.

Chapter 7: Conclusion and further studies of thesis work.

5. LITERATURE SURVEY

Many protocols were presented in literatures, to increase the fading channel performance in MANET.

Abu Sayed Md et al (2011) proposed the performance of two-hop wireless systems under Rayleigh and Nakagami-m fading channels for two widely used modulation schemes of 8-Phase Shift Keying (PSK) and 16-QAM of wireless communication systems. In their analysis, it was observed that the performance of the Rayleigh fading channel is worse than that of the Nakagami-m.

Yogender Singh Gill et al (2011) proposed Rayleigh fading model, in which they focus on NLOS communication, where the signal is received after several reflections and scattering. This work considers the Rician fading, which consists of LOS and found to be more applicable for satellite communication. Their work suggested that the Nakagami fading model is mostly suited for urban multipath propagation and it is sought to be the most practical model, specially used in mobile communication, where single bit data transmission was achieved assuming the channel to be Rayleigh faded with zero mean and variance 1. Finally it has been concluded that block bit transmission is more efficient than single bit transmission over Rician, Rayleigh and Nakagami fading channel with various modulation schemes.

Fawaz S. Al-Qahtani et al (2011) proposed the performance of a dual-hop Amplify-and-Forward (AF) relaying system with interference at both the relay and destination nodes. Although they considered that the Rayleigh fading is a popular statistical model, a more general model that encompasses a broad variety of fading scenarios is the Nakagami-fading model. Mainly they have investigated performance of interference-limited dual-hop CSI-assisted amplify-and-forward relaying in Nakagami- fading channels. The main contributions of this work include the derivation of the closed-form expression for the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the end-to-end Signal-to-Interference Noise Ratio (SINR) and obtained the exact closed-form expression for the outage probability of the system.

Basab B Purkayastha et al (2012) proposed the input signal under various fading conditions with certain modulations transmitted through Nakagami-m channels to evaluate the

performance of the 34 Digital Phase Locked Loop (DPLL) in terms of BER. This has been explained about the Nakagami-m distribution, which has gained widespread application in the modeling of physical fading radio channels. The primary justification of this work explained that the use of Nakagami-m fading model is a good fit to empirical fading data. In this model, it is noticed that with further increase of sampling frequency, the BER performance gets even better. Thus, this DPLL provides satisfactory performance in Nakagami -m fading channel with QPSK signal, using a carrier frequency 900 MHz with sampling frequency GHz.

6. RESEARCH SOLUTION

This research work focuses on design and development of a novel routing protocol for improving the fading channel performance of MANET. The entire research work carries out into two different stages where each stage is interrelated. In the first stage of the research work, a hybrid model is created by combining nakagami and weighbull fading channel for improving the performance of the fading channel. In the second stage of the research work, QPSK based Grover searching algorithm was implemented for upgrading the performance of fading channel.

In the first stage of research work, wired channels are completely characterized by their attenuation and time delay properties as a function of frequency, which are time invariants. However, wireless channels exhibit random and time variant channel characteristics. In order to characterize the fading channel, it is necessary to investigate its higher order fading statistics. This efficient model develops the Hybrid N.W. gamma Scheme, to reduce the fading problems in MANET. The effect of speed of nodes on key network performance matrices (i.e., average delay, throughput, jitter, and PDR) play very important role in the performance analysis and design of the mobile Ad-hoc network over the multipath fading environment for network performance of MANET. Emerging 3G and 4G mobile networks are designed to offer wide variety of services in hostile propagation environments.

Therefore, there is a need to identify additional fading parameters for channel characterization purpose. Tolerance time is defined as the short outage times, in which a

wireless communication system can tolerate satisfying the application dependent maximum value of Packet Error Rate (PER). By using this technique, a better result is obtained when compared to other existing technique.

The second stage of the research work focuses on the QPSK based Grover searching algorithm, based on node probability computation that can be applied to route searching in MANETs. Using parallel quantum phase-shift-keying (QPSK) scheme, Grover's searching algorithm can significantly reduce the required operating times. Traditional searching algorithms must overcome the problem, whereby too many paths need to be searched due to an oversized solution space. The main problem faced by Grover's searching algorithm is that the amplitude of the solution-path set is too small. Therefore, the core of QPSK based Grover searching algorithm determines how to make the amplitude rapidly centralize to a solution-path set, while considering the complexity and robustness of realizing the transformation. In other words, it is not difficult for Grover's searching algorithm to search all paths, and it focuses on how to reduce or eliminate the amplitude of non-solution paths, then converts the amplitude to solution paths in order to increase the measured probability of solution paths. By using this algorithm the fading problems of the MANET can reduce frequently when compared to the other recent techniques.

The results for the throughput, PDR, jitter, end to end delay shows that the Hybrid N.W Gaussian scheme is much better than the existing model. The data packet size is set to 512 bytes in all and each reported result is the average 300 second.

Figure 1 Comparison of proposed method with existing method

Figure 1 shows the comparison of novel hybrid method with other two existing methods. Thus proposed Hybrid N.W gamma scheme gives better results, when compared to other two existing methods.

Figure 2 through put ratio

Figure 2 indicates that the throughput ratio goes high. Thus the proposed novel Hybrid N.W scheme in fading problems gives better results, when compared to other existing methods.

Figure 3 PDR

Figure 3 shows the comparison of proposed novel method with other existing methods. Hence from the obtained graph, it will clear that the PDR goes high. Thus the proposed novel Hybrid N.W scheme in fading problems gives better results, when compared to other existing methods.

Figure 4 Jitter

Figure 4 shows the comparison of proposed novel method with other existing methods. Hence from the obtained graph, it will clear that the jitter value goes low. Thus the proposed novel Hybrid N.W scheme in fading problems gives better results, when compared to other existing methods.

In the second stage of experimental results, there is discussion about the results of the QPSK based Grover searching algorithm scheme without affecting its bandwidth efficiency based on implementation of TWDP fading channel. A comparison is made on the behalf of the results obtained by comparing the existing methodology.

Figure 5 Probability density function of TWDP fading Channel

Figure 5 illustrates that all the properties of probability density function are get together and is clear that the control of the transmitted signal for TWDP channel is deliberate over substantial range, which is the advantageous characteristic for an efficient system.

Figure 6 Number of channels Vs Average Bit error

Figure 6 shows the comparison of Number of channels with Average Bit error. From this comparison, it is clear that QPSK based Grover searching algorithm scheme has less average bit error occurred during the transmitted signal for fading channel in MANET. Hence the average bit error is less compared to existing methodologies.

Figure 7 Number of channels Vs Path Loss

Figure 7 shows the comparison of Number of channels with Path Loss. From this comparison, it is clear that QPSK based Grover searching algorithm scheme has minimize path loss compared to existing methods.

Figure 8 Number of channels Vs Total energy consumption

Figure 8 shows the comparison of Number of channels with Total energy consumption. From this comparison, QPSK based Grover searching algorithm scheme has low energy consumed during the transmitted signal for fading channel in MANET. Hence the Total energy consumption for proposed methodology is less than existing methodologies.

Figure 9 Number of channels Vs Packet Delivery Ratio

Figure 9 shows the comparison of Number of channels with Packet Delivery Ratio. From this comparison, QPSK based Grover searching algorithm scheme has high packet

delivery ratio during the transmitted signal for fading channel in MANET. Thus the Packet Delivery Ratio is high for proposed methodology compared to the existing methodologies.

Figure 10 Number of channels Vs data transmission rate

Figure 10 shows the comparison of Number of channels with data transmission rate. From this comparison, it is clear that QPSK based Grover searching algorithm scheme has maximized data transmission rate compared to existing methods.

7. SUMMARY

In the first stage of research work, the results for the throughput, PDR, jitter and end to end delay shows better performance compared to the existing models. It can also be concluded that the performance of Hybrid N.W gamma scheme improves by decreased in fading effect. This result is due to the change of the channel coherence duration: the increase of the average channel duration of good quality and the increase of that of poor quality. Thus the performance of Hybrid N.W Gamma scheme fading channel has shown that the end to end delay is inadequate for describing its performance for most applications of interest.. From the results, it is concluded that as the speed of user is increased, the amount of fading is increased

in the signal envelope. Therefore, as the speed of the nodes increases, more of the signal goes below the threshold and the amount of fading is increased. It is also concluded that the delay and jitter decreases, as the speed of the channel increases for the fading models. However, the mobile channel would like to develop another model for fading in mobile communication system, which will be reported in future communication. In the second stage of the research work, QPSK based Grover searching algorithm scheme is proposed for improving fading channel performance in MANET. It is clear that by altering the signal assemblage of the QPSK based Grover searching algorithm scheme using symbol-by-symbol detection, the performance is noticeably enhanced in the fading channel. Thus depending on the fading circumstances, a suitable interleaving depth can be effortlessly selected and the PDF of TWDP fading were articulated as convergent inestimable series and a low-complexity algorithm was developed for their appraisal.

8. REFERENCES

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